

Binary and Ternary Complexes of Beryllium(II) with Malonic, Amino, Thiodicarboxylic and Some Simple and Substituted Dicarboxylic Acids in Aqueous Medium*

D. N. SHELKE

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad-431 004

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The interaction of beryllium(II) with malonic, amino and thio acids in presence of some substituted and simple dicarboxylic acids has been studied. Mixed complexes of Be(II)-dicarboxylic acids with aspartic and thiomalic acids have been investigated. The distribution of the concentrations of simple and mixed species present, as a function of pH and other equilibrium constants have been utilized to explain the formation of mixed complexes. The estimation of stability constants by the relationship between complex stability and ligand basicity is discussed. The data point out that the slight differences present along the series of the complexes are not suppressed in the ternary ones.

THERE has been considerable upsurge in the last few years in the study of beryllium oxalate complexes¹⁻⁴. Interest in the beryllium complexes was recently shown by Verma *et al*⁵, with special reference to the binding sites of hydroxamic acids with the metal ion, in particular the kinetic and spectral study of beryllium bis complexes^{6,7}. The ternary systems of beryllium with iminodiacetic, dicarboxylic and hydroxy acids by Chaturvedi *et al*⁸ have also been reported.

Considering the biological significance of the amino^{9,10} and thiodicarboxylic acids¹¹⁻¹³, a study of the complexing ability of dicarboxylic acids with Be(II)-amino acids, thiodicarboxylic acid binary complexes and distribution of the complexes as a function of pH is worthwhile. However, to the best of our knowledge not a single system of the mixed-ligand complex formation between beryllium(II)-amino acid, thiodicarboxylic and some dicarboxylic acid has been studied so far. In view of the extensive review by Bertin *et al*^{14,15} on beryllium(II) complexes with variety of ligands, particularly dicarboxylic acids and their resulting structures, and the work reported in recent years by Thomas-David *et al*¹⁶⁻¹⁸ on the coordination behaviour of beryllium ion in binary complexes, the present study was undertaken to gain some insight in metal-ligand and ligand-ligand interactions, which could help an understanding of the role of beryllium ion in general, and in coordination compounds in particular. It was further felt that the mixed-ligand complexes of beryllium(II)-dicarboxylic acids with amino acids and thiodicarboxylic acids might also be interesting in biological systems¹⁹⁻²¹.

Experimental

Materials: The dicarboxylic acids such as malonic, methylmalonic, dimethylmalonic, succinic,

itaconic, maleic, glutaric and adipic, were obtained from Fluka (Germany) or were B.D.H., AnalaR grade products. Aspartic and thiomalic acids, obtained from B. D. H. (AnalaR) and Fluka (Germany) were biochemical and analytical reagents, respectively. All solutions were prepared in freshly double distilled water. Beryllium nitrate, (B.D.H., AnalaR) was used and its concentration was estimated gravimetrically²². The details of the other chemicals are described in our earlier papers²³⁻²⁵.

Measurements: Beryllium complex formation constants were calculated from potentiometric titration curves of the dicarboxylic, amino and thiodicarboxylic acids in absence and presence of beryllium. Changes in pH were followed with an Elico digital pH meter (L1-10 No. 1275), using glass and calomel electrodes. Titrations were carried out at various metal-ligand ratios from 1:1 to 1:5. All investigations were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere at 30° and ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO₄). For the calculation of the formation constants, a Fortran computer programme was used in putting at least 150 experimental data for each system. All computations were carried out at the IBM 370 Computer of the Indian Institute of Technology, Madras.

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation constants of the methylmalonic and dimethylmalonic acids and the stability constants of beryllium(II) binary complexes of these ligands under experimental conditions were evaluated by the method of Irving and Rossotti^{26,27}. The evaluated equilibrium constants (log K) for the beryllium complexes studied are presented in Table I, along with the literature values. In most of the cases stability constant values are comparable

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to the reported values ; the values, however, differ at different experimental conditions.

Beryllium(II) forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with all the ligands except glutaric and adipic acids in the pH range 2.5-5.0. A comparison of stability constants (Table 1) indicates that aspartic and methylmalonic acid complexes are more stable than those of simple dicarboxylic acids. The nature of the coordinating atoms for the ligands are similar and the observed stability constants are in the order expected by their basicities, ring size and the nature of the substituents, except in dimethylmalonic acid.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS (log K) FOR THE PARENT BINARY COMPLEXES OF BERYLLIUM(II)

$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$; $t = 30^\circ$

(Standard deviations are given in parentheses)

Ligand/acids	log K ₁	log K ₂
Malonic	5.15 (2)	3.90 (4)
	5.16 ^a	3.34 ^a
	5.35 ^b	3.60 ^b
Methylmalonic	5.21 (3)	3.46 (2)
Dimethylmalonic	4.88 (2)	3.40 (3)
Succinic	3.18 (2)	1.65 (4)
	3.08 ^d	—
	2.72 ^b	1.62 ^b
Itaconic	3.55 (2)	2.05 (3)
Thiomalic	4.80 (1)	3.17 (3)
	4.82 ^e	—
Aspartic	6.56 (2)	4.84 (2)
	6.54 ^f	4.81 ^f
Maleic	4.30 (1)	2.11 (4)
	4.33 ^e	2.13 ^e
Glutaric	3.04 (1)	—
Adipic	3.24 (3)	—
	3.24 ^e	—

a—ref. 16, b—ref. 47, c—ref. 48, d—ref. 49, e—ref. 50, f—ref. 51.

In addition to the carboxylate ions, the third potential donor sulphur and nitrogen atoms are present in thiomalic and aspartic acids. If chelation occurs through O—O of two carboxylate ions of these ligands, one would expect smaller formation constants, particularly in the order of the series of substituted succinic acids^{28,29}. Contrary to this, the observed higher values of equilibrium constants lead to the conclusion that coordination occurs through sulphur-oxygen and nitrogen-oxygen of thiomalic and aspartic acids, respectively. The donor sulphur atom in such complexes confers properties which are sometimes highly novel and differ markedly from those of the analogous oxygen derivatives. However, beryllium(II) being a hard acid, is a better oxygen binder than nitrogen, the high affinity of Be(II) for aspartic acid may be manifested by strong metal ion carboxylate binding³⁰. An additional factor favouring the stabilization of these complexes is the ring size, five membered and hence highly strained.

The concentrations of the various species H₂X, H₂Y, M²⁺, MX, MX₂²⁻, MY, MY₂²⁻ and MXY²⁻ and the different equilibrium constants were evaluated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Manning³¹ as outlined earlier³²⁻³⁴. The calculated con-

centrations of the species present and their corresponding equilibrium constants for a typical system, beryllium ion malonic (Y)-succinic (X) acid are given in Table 2. The average equilibrium constants calculated for other systems are set out in Tables 3-5.

TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF Be(II)-MALONIC (Y)-SUCCINIC (X)-ACID SYSTEM

$C_M = C_X = C_Y$ $\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$ $t = 30 \pm 0.1^\circ$					
$[H^+] \times 10^5$	K_{MXY}	β_{XY}	K_{DXY}	K_{2XY}	K_{2YX}
4.787	-1.813	8.777	4.423	3.627	5.597
4.267	-1.857	8.732	4.205	3.582	5.582
3.802	-1.800	8.791	4.215	3.641	5.564
3.389	-1.829	8.760	4.221	3.610	5.569
3.020	-1.853	8.736	4.199	3.586	5.574
2.692	-1.866	8.724	4.195	3.574	5.565
2.399	-1.875	8.714	4.209	3.595	5.561
2.318	-1.879	8.710	4.189	3.561	5.574
Average	-1.846	8.74 ± 0.03	4.204	3.594	5.566

The two equilibrium constants involving mixed ligand complexes is defined by Sigel³⁵ as $\Delta \log K$ (equation 1) which refers to the reaction and the disproportionation constant K_{DXY} (equation 2) as :

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{2XY} - \log K_{MY_1} = \log K_{2XY} - \log K_{MX_1} \dots (1)$$

$$K_{DXY} = 2 \log \beta_{MXY} - \log \beta_{MX_2} - \log \beta_{MY_2} \dots (2)$$

Thus $\Delta \log K$ is a measure of the affinity that Y has bonding to the aquated metal ion and to the complex (MX). Since more coordination sites are available for bonding the first ligand to a metal ion than for the second ligand, $\Delta \log K$ should in general be negative. As regards Be(II), usually having a coordination number of four, the expected value of $\Delta \log K$ would be -0.6, values markedly greater than this suggesting a stabilization of ternary complex. Statistically, a value (0.6) of K_{DXY} is to be expected so that the values greater than this indicate the preferential formation of mixed-ligand complexes. The value K_{DXY} is clearly dependent on the stabilities of the simple binary *bis*-complexes and since these *bis*-complexes are not intermediates in the formation of ternary complexes, the value of K_{DXY} may not truly reflect the stability of ternary complex.

In all the cases in Tables 3-5 the values of $\Delta \log K$ are negative, showing the stabilized nature of ternary complexes. However, a positive $\Delta \log K$ is obtained in malonic-succinic acid system which indicates the disproportionation reaction to be more on right side³⁶.

The important practical use of $\Delta \log K$ is to obtain an interesting relationship between complex stability and ligand basicity for the estimation of stability constants of ternary complexes. In the present investigation the data fit within experimental errors onto a straight line with a positive slope, even though in some of the series of basicities of the

TABLE 3—LOGARITHMS OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF BERYLLIUM(II)-DICARBOXYLIC-DICARBOXYLIC ACIDS SYSTEMS

Acid/systems	$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$		$t = 30^\circ$		$\Delta \log K$
	β_{XY}	K_{DXY}^a	K_{2XY}	K_{2YX}	
Malonic-succinic	8.74(8)	4.20	5.56	3.59	+0.41
Malonic-itaconic	8.02(2)	1.99	4.47	2.87	-0.70
Malonic-glutaric	7.41(1)	1.07 ^b	4.97	2.26	-0.78
Malonic-adipic	7.59(2)	1.05 ^b	4.95	2.44	-0.80
Malonic-maleic	8.70(2)	2.54	4.40	3.55	-0.75
Maleic-succinic	6.92(9)	2.60	3.74	2.62	-0.56
Maleic-itaconic	7.01(2)	2.01	3.46	2.71	-0.84

TABLE 4—LOGARITHMS OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF BERYLLIUM(II)-THIOMALIC (Y)-SECONDARY (X) LIGANDS

Secondary ligand (X)	$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$		$t = 30^\circ$		$\Delta \log K$
	β_{XY}	K_{DXY}	K_{2XY}	K_{2YX}	
Malonic	8.22(2)	0.02	9.07	3.42	-1.73
Methylmalonic	8.70(4)	0.76	3.47	3.90	-1.31
Dimethylmalonic	8.47(9)	0.69	3.59	3.67	-1.20
Succinic	6.99(4)	1.18	3.51	1.89	-0.99
Itaconic	7.15(2)	0.78	3.60	2.35	-1.20
Maleic	8.45(3)	2.52	4.15	3.65	-0.68
Glutaric	6.69(1)	0.48 ^b	3.65	1.89	-1.15
Adipic	6.68(2)	0.27 ^b	3.44	1.89	-1.36

ligands, differ by several orders of magnitude. In fact, it follows unequivocally for the plots of complex stability and ligand basicity that slopes of any kind are possible. Subsequently, in an elegant study on mixed-ligand complexes, Sigel²⁷ succeeded in obtaining a straight line relationship between these two quantities for ternary complexes of transition metal ions with a variety of ligands for which no single straight line is entirely satisfactory^{28,29}. During the characterization of binding sites of dipeptides to the metal ions³⁰⁻³², we noticed this interesting aspect of the ternary complexes, and in particular copper(II)-glycyl-phenyl alanine-amino acids³³.

It can be seen (Figs. 1 and 2), that the point corresponding to maleic acid shows extra stabilization from the straight lines expected for the series of closely related ligands. However, other straight lines are also possible if maleic acid is taken into consideration. As a result of this the magnitude is also changed especially in the systems with aspartic and thiomalic acids as primary ligands. Because of its double bond character, maleic acid is deviated from the expected straight lines, indicating relatively stabilized nature of the ternary complexes than the binary analogous. The basicity of the ligands is sensitive towards π electron distribution even though hydrogen is bound only by a σ bond. That complex stability is dependent upon π electron distribution is well known³⁴⁻³⁶.

Fig. 1. Relation between $\Delta \log K$ and $pK_{H_2A}^H + pK_{HA}^H$ for the ternary complexes of Be(II)-thiomalic-dicarboxylic acids, where dicarboxylic acids are: (1) succinic, (2) itaconic, (3) maleic, (4) glutaric, (5) adipic, (6) malonic, (7) methylmalonic and (8) dimethylmalonic. $\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$ and $t = 30^\circ$.

Fig. 2. Relation between $\Delta \log K$ and $pK_{H_2A}^H + pK_{HA}^H$ for the ternary complexes of Be(II)-aspartic-dicarboxylic acids, where dicarboxylic acids are: (1) succinic, (2) itaconic, (3) maleic, (4) glutaric, (5) adipic, (6) thiomalic, (7) malonic and (8) methylmalonic. $\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$, $t = 30^\circ$.

To extend these observations further, we examined this relationship considering maleic acid as a primary ligand. All the points invariably fall on a straight line of a positive slope except for methylmalonic and dimethylmalonic acids. It is reasonable to expect that these deviated points would indicate the sterically hindered complexes of beryllium(II) also.

The values for K_{DXY} from the experimental data are significantly greater than 0.6, indicating that the mixed-ligand complexes are much more stable. The values of K_{DXY} (Table 5) in aspartic-itaconic, aspartic-glutaric and aspartic-thiomalic acid systems are substantially lower than expected. The higher

stability constants of binary complexes, particularly in aspartic-thiomalic acid system, result into the relative lower values. The highest value of K_{DXY} i.e. 4.20 obtained in malonic-succinic acid system accompanied by high value of stability of the mixed complex is also understandable.

TABLE 5—LOGARITHMS OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF BERYLLIUM(II)-ASPARTIC (Y)-SECONDARY (X) LIGANDS

$\mu=0.1 M (NaClO_4)$; $t=80^\circ$

(Standard deviations are given in parentheses)

Secondary ligand (X)	β_{XY}	K_{DXY}	K_{2XY}	K_{2YX}	$\Delta \log K$
Malonic	10.42(4)	0.99	5.27	3.86	-1.29
Methylmalonic	10.88(5)	1.63	5.64	4.28	-0.92
Succinic	8.27(4)	0.81	5.09	1.71	-1.47
Itaconic	8.47(2)	0.06	4.92	1.92	-1.64
Thiomalic	9.22(2)	0.98	4.88	2.66	-2.18
Maleic	10.29(3)	2.77	5.99	3.78	-0.57
Glutaric	7.91(8)	0.09 ^b	4.87	1.95	-1.69
Adipic	8.28(1)	0.15 ^b	4.69	1.68	-1.57

A comparison of K_{2XY} and K_{2YX} values in the systems studied shows the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary. The values of K_{2XY} and K_{2YX} reveal the formation of mixed complexes is much more than corresponding binary. However, the systems involving itaconic, glutaric and thiomalic acids (Table 5) as secondary ligands show destabilization of mixed complexes. The observation of relatively higher stabilities of aspartic and thiomalic acids may be taken to imply the presence of an amino group or sulphhydryl group. Further, we would like to point out that the effect of different donor groups experienced by a Be(II) ion is manifested by strong metal carboxylate bond. The addition of methyl groups in malonic acid to an existing substituent effect simply contributes a more sterically hindered effect experienced by the metal ion.

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